

Disease resistance

were used as checks. BR5 has fine aromatic grains. BR7 has long nonaromatic grains; Kataribhog has long aromatic grains but unsatisfactory yield.

Most of the lines varied widely in the visual scores — only 15 were scored 3 to 5 and none were scored 1. Fifty lines scored 7 and 54 lines, 9. Variability was observed for all characters studied. The table lists 15 selections equivalent to or better than the standard checks. All of the selected lines had numerically higher elongation-ratio values than the checks. But 12 selections had similar or higher imbibition ratio values, and most were equivalent to the checks in visual scores. ■

Elongation ratio, imbibition ratio, and visual score of selected aromatic IR424 lines. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1978.

Pedigree	Elongation ratio	Imbibition ratio	Visual score ^a
IR424-2-1			
/J1-30-6	2.00	3.98	3
/J1-30-7	1.98	3.95	3
/J1-30-8	1.88	3.76	3
/J7-2-4	1.85	3.69	3
/J7-2-5	1.75	3.77	3
/J7-2-7	1.85	2.61	5
/J7-2-9	1.85	3.69	3
/J7-2-15	1.85	2.74	5
/J7-4-11	1.76	2.52	5
/J7-4-14	1.82	3.62	3
/J7-4-15	2.00	4.31	3
/J8-1-8	2.07	4.47	3
/J8-1-9	2.00	3.98	3
/J8-1-18	2.01	4.35	3
/J8-7-14	1.88	4.07	3
BR5	1.70	3.58	3
BR7 ^b	1.40	3.60	3
Kataribhog	1.67	4.18	3

^a1 = All cooked grains smooth and uniform in length; 3 = 80% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 5 = 60% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 7 = 40% cooked grains smooth, uniform; 9 = 20% cooked grains smooth, uniform.

^bNonaromatic.

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Rice cultures that are moderately resistant to Helminthosporiose

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Helminthosporiose is widespread in Tamil Nadu. The disease affects the [rice crop at all growth stages; no cultivated variety is resistant or tolerant. The 540 IET entries received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for reaction to high pressure of helminthosporiose in a semidry nursery. The entries were grown in 2 rows, 1 In long, surrounded by 1 row of the susceptible check Benibhog. At 45 days of age the plants were spray inoculated with a conidial suspension (concn of 40,000 spores/ml) of *Helminthosporium oryzae* that had been isolated from typical lesions. The disease incidence was scored on a 0-9 scale. Benibhog had a score of 9 (highly susceptible) and many entries scored from 5 to 7. Five entries — IET5870, IET5878, IET6515, IET6524, and IET6541 — were scored from 0 to 1. When tested in the laboratory under similar inoculum pressure, the cultures showed moderate resistance to the disease (score, lower than 3). ■

Resistance of cultivars to the rice leaf folder

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Eleven standard cultivars and four promising lines were evaluated for resistance to the rice leaf folder in a randomized block design replicated three times in a field trial in 1977 kharif. In the last week of August, when leaf folder incidence was at a peak, all the leaves and those infested on 15 hills/replication

were counted and the percentage of infestation was recorded.

Infestation ranged from 13 to 63%; it was highest on Jaya and lowest on Prasad (see table). No cultivar was immune to leaf folder attack. ■

Susceptibility of rice cultivars to the rice leaf folder. Pantnagar, India.

Designation	Av infestation (%)
Jaya	63
IR8	61
Padma	57
UPR190D-17-1	55
IR20	52
UPR173-23	49
UPR82-1-7	49
Cauvery	42
Bala	38
Saket-4	36
Tilak chandan (dwarf (mutant))	31
Ratna	30
Pusa 2-21	24
IR24	15
Prasad	13
CD at 5%	17.55

Straighthead disease of rice suspected in southern Thailand

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Severe symptoms similar to those of straighthead disease reported in the USA and Japan were observed in southern Thailand in 1977. The observations were made in an 80-ha area of lowland rice planted on sandy soil that was previously planted to upland crops in Ronphibool subprovince, Nakornsrithamaraj province. The rice plants were at the heading stage. The infected plants had normal vegetative growth but exhibited tillering at the upper nodes, poor exertion, twisted spikelets, distorted hulls (in "parrot beak" shape), and high sterility.